

Language Performance in English and Test Anxiety Among Pre-Service Education Students

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RESEARCH ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: January 31, 2023 Reviewed: May 21, 2024 Accepted: June 03, 2024 Published: June 28, 2024</p> <p> Copyright © 2025 by the Author(s). This open-access article is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>	<p>This study aimed to determine the test anxiety level of the pre-service education students in terms of emotionality and worriedness about their language performance in English. The study also examined the relationship between the level of worriedness and emotionality of the pre-service education students. The study was conducted at a university in Echague, Isabela, Philippines. There were 264 respondents as the selected sample size. English Proficiency Test and Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI) were utilized as research instruments in the study. With the use of the SPSS, data were analyzed. The findings of this study revealed that pre-service education students had a high level of anxiety during the test. Likewise, there was a significant relationship between test anxiety and language performance in English. This study provided information about test anxiety that would allow administrators and teacher leaders to lead schools to excellence. It is expected to generate social change by leading to changes in curriculum and instructional strategies. The results could also aid in the development of prevention and intervention programs, which, in turn, could decrease test anxiety and increase students' success.</p>

Keywords: *emotionality, test anxiety, test anxiety inventory, worry*

Introduction

The Philippines is recognized globally as one of the largest English-speaking nations. Based on the Business English Index (BEI) in 2012, only the Philippines

attained a score above 7.0, putting the country within the range of a high proficiency that indicates an ability to lead business discussions and perform complex tasks. The country's proficiency in the English language is one of the strengths that has helped drive the economy and even made the Philippines the top voice outsourcing destination in the world, surpassing India in 2012. According to Mitra (2013), the Philippines' principal strength in the export service sector is the large, educated workforce with strong English language capabilities.

Despite being recognized as the top English-speaking nation, it is in contrast with the study conducted by Navarro et al. (2015) and Leyaley (2016). Navarro et al. (2015) found that Maritime students agreed that English is required in their chosen course and is useful in securing a job, especially in the Metro Manila area and abroad. On the other hand, Maritime students were incompetent in vocabulary and reading comprehension and fairly incompetent in grammar. Further, Baeta et al. (2012) at Central Bicol State University revealed in their study that College Freshmen were proficient in grammar and moderately proficient both in reading comprehension and phonology, but they were hardly proficient in vocabulary. Generally, the proficiency level of college freshmen fell under moderate proficiency.

In the study conducted by Leyaley (2016) in Kalinga-Apayao, she found that the English language proficiency of freshmen students who were enrolled in the Institute of Teacher Education is described as early intermediate regardless of the type of school they graduated from, the program they were enrolled in, and the honors they had received. This means that they could communicate basic and familiar topics containing previously taught vocabulary and sentence structures. On the other hand, they commonly made errors in word usage, pronunciation, and grammar. Thus, they greatly benefitted from explicit teaching and modeling of high-frequency words, grammatical structures, and sentence frames (Baeta et al., 2012). Using the English language as the medium of communication and in test-taking instills in them feelings of uneasiness, frustration, self-doubt, insecurity, or apprehension.

Thus, evidently in the study they found that students' performance in the English language can be regarded as average – not high and not low – since they demonstrated moderate levels of both English language anxiety and self-efficacy. Therefore, if students have experienced a high level of English language anxiety, their performance in the English language will be poor. Conversely, if students had experienced a low level of English language anxiety, their performance in the English language will be better than third class upper division or higher than 69%. Thus, English language anxiety is a major factor that negatively affected students' performance in the English language (Anyadubalu, 2010).

Test anxiety (TA) can be conceptualized as “a perceived intellectual incompetency and a defensive ploy to ward off low self-evaluation” (Zeidner, 1998, p. 81). Liebert and Morris (1967) proposed that TA consists of two major components: “worry” and “emotionality”. Worry is the cognitive component of TA referring to concerns about being evaluated and about the consequences of failure. In contrast, an affective component labeling “emotionality” refers to the perception of autonomic reactions evoked by the test situation. Worry is more correlated with academic performance than emotionality (Liebert & Morris, 1967). Spielberger (1972) also viewed test anxiety as a situation-specific form of trait anxiety.

Moreover, Salehi and Marefat (2014) researched foreign language anxiety (FLA) and TA among Iranian students at a language institute. Of the 200 participants, 193 were female, and their ages ranged between 14 and 47. The authors found a negative

correlation between both FLA and test scores and TA and test scores. That is to say, the participants suffered debilitating anxiety. Cheng et al. (2014) also studied the effects of student motivation and TA on three different standardized high-stakes language tests. They studied over a thousand Chinese-speaking participants and found that both motivation and TA influenced test performance. Female respondents showed greater TA, as did those participants who stated that the exam was important to them.

Another Turkish study, by Gursoy and Arman (2016), was carried out among 138 high school students who were taking an EFL class. The study was both quantitative, using an anxiety scale to determine TA, and qualitative, gathering data through interviews. The participants showed a moderate level of TA but mentioned in the interviews that several factors contributed to an increase in their anxiety. Among these factors were feeling unprepared for the exam and having time limits.

At the university where this study was carried out, the objectives were to find out the test anxiety level of pre-service education students in terms of emotionality and worriedness. It also determined the language performance in English of the pre-serve education students and ascertained the relationship between the language performance in English of pre-service education in terms of worriedness and emotionality. It also examined the relationship between the level of worriedness and emotionality of the pre-service education students.

It is expected that the results of this study would contribute to the knowledge in the field of teacher education. Most of the current test anxiety studies focused on secondary education (Sapp, 1996). Knowing how test anxiety and standardized test performance are related could help improve teachers', administrators', and parents' understanding of test anxiety. It could help them become more aware of the external and internal factors that could affect standardized test scores. This study provided information about test anxiety that will allow administrators and teacher leaders to lead schools to excellence. It is expected to generate social change by leading to changes in curriculum and instructional strategies. The results could also aid in the development of prevention and intervention programs, which, in turn, could decrease test anxiety and increase students' success.

Methods

The data was collected personally by the researcher with prior arrangement with the department concerned and teachers. Intact classes were used for this purpose. To avoid any measurement-related error, standardization of procedure was ensured by giving uniform instruction to students each time the data was collected. Similar instruction, environment, and execution timing were provided to students in each department during data collection. The consent of the participants, the privacy of information to be collected, and other ethical sureties were provided to the participants.

The researcher used convenience sampling to select the respondents of the study. There was a population size of 840 students, 264 of which were selected as the sample size of the study at 95% degree of confidence and 5% allowable error (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). After getting the sample size of the respondents, they were in turn distributed proportionately to the different year levels using the proportionate allocation formula.

As shown in Table 1, a total of 264 students served as the respondents of the study.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Program	Number of Respondents	Sample Size	Percentage
BSEd	320	101	38.00
BEEd	240	75	28.00
BPEd	160	50	19.00
BTLEd	120	38	15.00
Total	840	264	100

Data were analyzed by using SPSS- Software Package. Descriptive statistics was used for the descriptive values for emotionality scale scores, worry scale scores, total test anxiety scale scores, and language performance scores for male and female students in different grade levels or it provided an understanding of the dimensions of data while Kendall's Tau b was focused on finding the relationship of emotionality scale, worry scale, and TAI total score with pre-service education students' language performance in English as described in research questions.

A validated assessment instrument, the Spielberger Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI), was adopted and administered to all participating students. The TAI is a self-report questionnaire of 20 statements in which respondents are asked to report how often they experience anxiety symptoms before, during, and after taking tests. Each statement response is scored with a four-point Likert scale (1-4) yielding a total test anxiety score ranging from 20 to 80 points. The TAI also yields two subscale scores that measure worry and emotionality, the two major components of test anxiety that reflect the cognitive concerns and emotional responses associated with the evaluation of stress.

The language performance of the respondents was measured through an English Proficiency Test which is designed to assess their stress and intonation, verbal ability, reading comprehension, correct usage, identifying errors, spelling and punctuation, and logical organization.

The scores of the respondents were transmuted to the grade description of the university, as follows: 1.00=98-100; 1.25=95-97; 1.75=89-91; 2.0=86-88; 2.25=80-82; 2.75=77-79; 3.0=75-76; 5.00 below 74 (Failure); and INC. = requirements not fully met.

Ethical Considerations

Those who participated in the survey had to have a prior agreement with the department concerned and teachers. It was voluntary and well-informed consent. Collected, the participants' consent, the confidentiality of information, and other ethical guarantees given to the participants.

Results and Discussion**Table 2. Test Anxiety Level of the Pre-service Education Students**

Test Anxiety Inventory	Mean	Description
Emotionality		
1. While taking the test, I had an uneasy, upset feeling.	2.91	Often
2. I felt very jittery when taking the test.	2.92	Often
3. Even when I've well prepared for a test, I feel very nervous about it.	2.95	Often
4. I'll start feeling uneasy just before getting my test scores back.	2.78	Often
5. During the test I felt very tense.	3.02	Often
6. I felt very panicky when I took the test.	2.89	Often
7. I worried a great deal before taking the test.	2.86	Often
8. I felt my heart beating very fast during the test.	2.86	Often
Grand mean	2.90	Often
Worry		
1. Thinking about the score I'd get interfered with my work on the test.	2.95	Often
2. I froze up on the test.	2.96	Often
3. During the test I found myself thinking about whether I'll get into graduate school.	2.89	Often
4. The harder I worked at taking the test, the more confused I got.	2.88	Often
5. Thoughts of doing poorly interfered with my concentration on the test.	3.06	Often
6. I seem to defeat myself while working on texts.	2.88	Often
7. During the test I found myself thinking about the consequences of failing.	2.89	Often
8. During the test I got so nervous that I forgot facts I really know.	2.89	Often
Grand mean	2.93	Often
Overall Anxiety Level		
1. I felt unsure and tense while taking the test.	2.86	Often
2. I wish that examinations did not bother me so much.	2.86	Often
3. During the test I was so tense that my stomach got upset.	2.95	Often
4. The test was over I tried to stop worrying about it, but I just couldn't.	2.96	Often
Grand mean	2.91	Often

The table shows the test anxiety level of the pre-service education students.

Emotionality. As seen in the table, the mean ratings from 2.78 to 3.02 revealed that the pre-service students often had uneasy, upset feelings and felt very jittery while taking the test. Moreover, even when they had prepared well for a test, oftentimes, they became worried a great deal and felt very nervous before taking the test. During the test, more often than not, they felt their hearts heart beating very fast and even felt very

panicky and very tense. The pre-service education students affirmed that they oftentimes started feeling uneasy just before getting their test scores back. The grand mean is 2.90 indicating that they were often very emotional when it came to test taking.

Worry. The means ratings from 2.88 to 3.06 with a grand mean rating of 2.93 revealed that the pre-service students often become very worried during test taking, specifically, more frequently. The harder they worked at taking the test, the more confused they became. They frequently froze up on the test and seemed to defeat themselves while working on texts and thinking about the score they would get often interfered with their work on the test. During the test, the pre-service students often found themselves thinking about whether they would get into graduate school and the consequences of failing. Oftentimes their thoughts of doing poorly interfered with their concentration on the test and even got so nervous that they forgot facts they really knew beforehand.

Overall Anxiety Level. Table 2 also describes the overall anxiety level of the pre-service students. As indicated, the mean ratings from 2.86 to 2.96 resulting in a grand mean rating of 2.91 revealed that they were generally very anxious during test-taking. Oftentimes, they wished that examinations do not bother them so much, they frequently felt unsure and tense while taking the test, felt so tense that their stomach got upset often and when the test was over, they also tried to stop worrying about it, but oftentimes, they just could not do it. Findings agree with the study of Abbott (2009) that all students surveyed reported noticeable levels of anxiety when taking tests. According to McDonald (2010), test anxiety is grouped under a category of anxious states and negative emotions that are often associated with neuroticism. Additionally, since test anxiety often develops out of fear of negative evaluation, it is like a social phobia, which causes fears of being negatively judged. These students may spend more of their time worrying about the outcome of the test and how others will judge their performance than on the test itself.

Table 3. Language Performance in English of the Pre-Service Education Students

Area	Score	GPA	Description
1. Stress and Intonation	71.13	4.00	Conditional
2. Verbal Ability	75.92	3.00	Passed
3. Reading Comprehension	78.25	3.00	Passed
4. Correct Usage	75.01	3.00	Passed
5. Identifying Errors	66.58	5.00	Failure
6. Spelling and Punctuation	81.09	2.50	Passed
Overall Performance in English	74.66	3.00	Passed

Table 3 shows the language performance in English of the pre-service education students, in general, and specifically as to stress and intonation, verbal ability, reading comprehension, correct usage, identifying errors, and spelling and punctuation. As gleaned from the table, the final score of 74.55 was equivalent to a Grade-Point Average

(GPA) of 3.00 indicating they merely passed. Specifically, it can be noted that the pre-service students got the highest score of 81.09 in spelling and punctuation equivalent to a GPA of 2.50. They also passed in verbal ability, reading comprehension, and correct usage, with corresponding scores of 75.92, 78.25, and 75.01, which were equivalent to a GPA of 3.00 or “passed”. The lowest grade obtained by the pre-service students was 66.58 or equivalent to a GPA of 5.00 indicating a failing grade in identifying errors.

Table 4. Relationship Between Pre-Service Education Students’ Emotionality Level and Their Language Performance in English

Emotionality Inventory	Stress and Intonation		Verbal Ability		Reading Comprehension		Correct Usage		Identifying Errors		Spelling and Punctuation		Overall Performance	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
1. While taking the test, I had an uneasy, upset feeling.	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.11	-0.15 [*]	0.00	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.90	0.02 ^{ns}	0.68	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.17	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.51	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.11
2. I felt very jittery when taking the test.	0.07 ^{ns}	0.18	0.05 ^{ns}	0.37	0.00 ^{ns}	0.99	0.02 ^{ns}	0.66	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.87	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.38	0.02 ^{ns}	0.64
3. Even when I've well prepared for a test, I feel very nervous about it.	0.01 ^{ns}	0.88	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.50	0.05 ^{ns}	0.27	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.63	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.49	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.39	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.55
4. I'll start feeling uneasy just before getting my test scores back.	0.01 ^{ns}	0.80	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.26	0.01 ^{ns}	0.77	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.76	0.08 ^{ns}	0.09	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.56	0.00 ^{ns}	0.98
5. During the test I felt very tense.	0.05 ^{ns}	0.31	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.79	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.56	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.09	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.19	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.41	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.25
6. I felt very panicky when I took the test.	0.06 ^{ns}	0.21	0.03 ^{ns}	0.51	0.03 ^{ns}	0.55	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.81	0.07 ^{ns}	0.13	0.04 ^{ns}	0.43	0.06 ^{ns}	0.24
7. I worried a great deal before taking the test.	-0.10 [*]	0.05	0.09 ^{ns}	0.08	0.04 ^{ns}	0.46	0.03 ^{ns}	0.54	0.09 ^{ns}	0.07	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.51	0.01 ^{ns}	0.80
8. I felt my heart beating very fast during the test.	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.65	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.77	-0.10 [*]	0.04	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.13	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.39	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.58	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.11
Grand mean	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.77	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.55	0.00 ^{ns}	0.97	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.84	0.02 ^{ns}	0.72	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.26	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.55

Table 4 to 6 indicates the relationship between pre-service education students’ level of anxiety in terms of test taking emotionality and worry and their language performance in English.

As shown in Table 4, the pre-service students’ performance in stress and intonation was significantly related to their level of getting worried before taking the test. The correlation value of -0.10 with a 0.05 significance level revealed an inverse association, that is, there is a tendency that when the pre-service students less worry before taking their test, the higher is their possibility of obtaining higher grades in stress and intonation.

In the same way, the correlation value of -0.15 with a 0.05 significance level revealed an indirect and significant relationship between the performance in verbal ability and the feeling of uneasiness or upset in test taking. Thus, the higher the chance of the pre-service students, garnering a higher grade in verbal ability when they feel more relaxed and do not experience uneasy or upset feelings when taking their examination. Likewise, the reading comprehension performance of the pre-service students will likely increase when they tend to have a lesser feeling of their hearts beating very fast during the test. The pre-service students’ performance in, correct usage, identifying errors, and spelling and punctuation were not associated with the emotionality of the pre-service students when taking their examinations. This was revealed by the correlation values from -0.08 to 0.09 with significance levels greater than 0.05.

Considering the overall English performance of the pre-service students, the correlation values from -0.08 to 0.06 with significance levels greater than 0.05 revealed that it had no significant association with their emotionality level.

Table 5. Relationship Between Pre-Service Education Students' Worry Level and Their Language Performance in English

Worry Inventory	Stress and Intonation		Verbal Ability		Reading Comprehension		Correct Usage		Identifying Errors		Spelling and Punctuation		Overall Performance	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
1. Thinking about the score I'd get interfered with my work on the test.	0.04 ^{ns}	0.44	0.00 ^{ns}	0.95	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.74	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.31	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.16	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.31	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.47
2. I froze up on the test.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.91	0.03 ^{ns}	0.62	0.04 ^{ns}	0.45	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.08	0.05 ^{ns}	0.28	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.38	0.00 ^{ns}	0.93
3. During the test I found myself thinking about whether I'll get into graduate school.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.80	0.02 ^{ns}	0.63	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.70	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.80	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.47	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.63	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.54
4. The harder I worked at taking the test, the more confused I got.	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.18	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.41	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.78	-0.14 [*]	0.01	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.15	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.10	-0.10 [*]	0.03
5. Thoughts of doing poorly interfered with my concentration on the test.	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.52	-0.13 [*]	0.01	-0.10 [*]	0.04	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.15	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.18	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.55	-0.11 [*]	0.02
6. I seem to defeat myself while working on texts.	0.08 ^{ns}	0.13	0.00 ^{ns}	0.94	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.42	-0.10 [*]	0.04	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.45	0.07 ^{ns}	0.18	0.02 ^{ns}	0.72
7. During the test I found myself thinking about the consequences of failing.	0.02 ^{ns}	0.67	0.01 ^{ns}	0.89	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.35	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.23	0.00 ^{ns}	1.00	0.05 ^{ns}	0.31	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.69
8. During the test I got so nervous that I forgot facts I really know.	0.06 ^{ns}	0.21	0.03 ^{ns}	0.51	0.03 ^{ns}	0.55	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.81	0.07 ^{ns}	0.13	0.04 ^{ns}	0.43	0.06 ^{ns}	0.24
Grand mean	0.02 ^{ns}	0.72	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.86	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.47	-0.10 [*]	0.02	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.65	0.00 ^{ns}	0.95	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.44

The correlation values from -0.13 and -0.10 with significance levels less than 0.05 reveal significant and indirect associations between pre-service teachers' performance in verbal ability and reading comprehension and in their level of thoughts of doing poorly which interfered with their concentration on the test. This implies that reducing thoughts of performing poorly can help improve concentration during the test, likely leading to better performance in verbal ability and reading comprehension.

Their performance in correct usage had also an indirect association with some aspects of their worry level when taking the test. More specifically, the correlation values of -0.14 and -0.10 with significance levels less than 0.05 implied that when their feelings of being more confused when they tried working harder as well as when their feeling of defeat while working on text in the test were lessened, the higher chances they would obtain better grades in correct usage. In general, it was noted that their overall performance in English would tend to increase when their overall level of worry in test taking decreased as indicated by the correlation value of -0.10 with 0.02 level of significance.

Lastly, the correlation values of -0.10 and -0.11 with significance levels less than 0.05 also revealed a significant and indirect association between pre-service students' overall performance in English and their being more confused when they tried to work harder in the exam as well as when inferences of the thoughts of doing poorly with their concentration on the test. This result implied further that when these attitudes are manifested less in themselves, there is a tendency that they will obtain higher overall performance in English.

Table 6. Relationship Between Pre-Service Education Students' Overall Anxiety and Their Language Performance in English

Overall Anxiety Inventory	Stress and Intonation		Verbal Ability		Reading Comprehension		Correct Usage		Identifying Errors		Spelling and Punctuation		Overall Performance	
	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.	Corr.	Sig.
1. I felt unsure and tense while taking the test.	-0.10*	0.05	0.09 ^{ns}	0.08	0.04 ^{ns}	0.46	0.03 ^{ns}	0.54	0.09 ^{ns}	0.07	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.51	0.01 ^{ns}	0.80
2. I wish examinations did not bother me so much.	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.65	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.77	-0.10*	0.04	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.13	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.39	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.58	-0.08 ^{ns}	0.11
3. During the test I was so tense that my stomach got upset.	0.04 ^{ns}	0.44	0.00 ^{ns}	0.95	-0.02 ^{ns}	0.74	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.31	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.16	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.31	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.47
4. The test was over I tried to stop worrying about it, but I just couldn't.	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.91	0.03 ^{ns}	0.62	0.04 ^{ns}	0.45	-0.09 ^{ns}	0.08	0.05 ^{ns}	0.28	-0.05 ^{ns}	0.38	0.00 ^{ns}	0.93
Grand mean	-0.04 ^{ns}	0.34	0.05 ^{ns}	0.34	-0.01 ^{ns}	0.85	-0.07 ^{ns}	0.15	0.01 ^{ns}	0.85	-0.06 ^{ns}	0.24	-0.03 ^{ns}	0.47

Table 6 shows the relationship between pre-service education students' overall anxiety level and their language performance in English. As gleaned from the table, the feeling of being unsure and tense while taking the test had a significant but inverse association with the pre-service students' performance in stress and intonation with a correlation value of -0.10 and 0.05 significance level. Hence, there was a chance they would achieve higher grades in this area if they felt less unsure and tense while taking the test.

Additionally, the correlation value of -0.10 with a 0.04 significance level also implied a significant but indirect association between the level of how the pre-service students wished that examinations would not bother them so much. The less they wished that their examinations did not bother them so much, the higher their possibility of obtaining better reading comprehension performance. In general, their overall performance in English had no bearing in all aspects of their overall anxiety level, as indicated by the correlation values from -0.08 to 0.03 with significance levels greater than 0.05.

The above-mentioned findings conformed with Ray (1974), who found that a lower level of anxiety motivated students to achieve higher achievement, whereas a higher level of anxiety became an obstacle to achieving higher achievement. Results also showed that a cognitive factor (worry) contributes more to test anxiety than an affective factor (emotional). Therefore, it is concluded that test anxiety is one of the factors that are responsible for students' underachievement and low performance, but it can be managed by appropriate training of students in dealing with factors causing test anxiety.

Table 7. Relationship Between Pre-Service Education Students' Overall Level of Worriedness and Emotionality

Anxiety Level	Overall Emotionality	
	Corr.	Sig.
Overall Worriedness	0.61*	0.00

*Significant

As shown in Table 7, the overall level of worriedness and emotionality of the pre-service education students was found to be significantly and directly associated, with a correlation value of 0.61 with 0.00 level of significance. Hence, this implied that as their level of emotionality increases, chances were, their level of worriedness would also tend to increase. The more they felt distressed or tremendously afraid to take an examination, the greater the possibility that they would become more worried or distressed about the outcome of their performance. This finding was supported by the study of Eubank (1993) who stated that as the fear component of test anxiety increased in the students, the worry component of test anxiety increased in them.

Conclusion and Future Works

This study assessed the language performance and test anxiety among the pre-service education students at Isabela State University. The level of emotionality revealed that the pre-service students felt very nervous, very panicky, feeling uneasy before getting their test scores back. The results also implied that they were often very emotional when it comes to test-taking.

The level of worry indicated that thoughts about the consequences of failing often disrupted their concentration during the test, making them so nervous that they sometimes forgot previously learned facts. On the other hand, the language performance of the pre-service education students passed on the spelling punctuation, verbal ability, reading comprehension, and correct usage.

The relationship between the anxiety level and language performance in English on stress and intonation is significantly related to their level of getting worried before the test-taking. Likewise, the reading comprehension performances of the pre-service education students would likely increase when they tend to have a lesser feeling of their heart beats very fast during the test. On the correct usage, identifying errors and spelling and punctuation were not associated with the emotionality of the pre-service education students.

The correlation between worry levels and verbal ability and reading comprehension suggests that reducing thoughts of performing poorly, which can interfere with test concentration, will likely lead to improved performance in verbal ability and reading comprehension. On the overall performance in English, the pre-service students were confused when they tried to work harder and their thoughts interfered that they did poorly on the test, it implied that when these attitudes were manifested less in themselves, there was a tendency that they would obtain higher overall performance in English. Feeling unsure and tense during the test negatively affected their performance in stress and intonation. However, reducing these feelings could increase their chances of obtaining higher grades.

With regard to the correlational overall level of worriedness and emotionality of the pre-service education students, as their level of emotionality increased, chances were, their level of worriedness would also tend to increase.

In general, their performance in English was manageable if their anxiety was less during the test, they tended to obtain a higher performance on the test. To decrease the test anxiety of the pre-service education students, encourage the students to prepare for the examinations in advance to handle and cope with test anxiety before and during examinations. Proper guidance and understanding could also be made as there are some students who need a motivating factor that will reduce their test anxiety. Likewise, engage the students to join the different social activities as well as practice tests and

continuous assessment to avoid and control panicking and nervousness which most likely trigger anxiety. Similar studies should also be undertaken to understand better the relationship between test anxiety and language performance in English of pre-service education students.

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